

Final Report

DALLAS ZOO
 Vet: JAN RAINES
 650 S. RL THORNTON FWY
 DALLAS, TX 75203

Case#: 16-34248
 Accessioned: 05/13/16
 Report Generated: 05/23/16 @ 3:01 PM by CF3
 Results Last Modified: 05/23/16 @ 9:12 AM

Case ID	Owner	Coordinator	
Dallas Zoo - 16T119	DALLAS ZOO	ALLENDER	
Breed	Species	Sex / Fixed	Age
Snake Breed NOS	Snake NOS	Not Given / R	

Wildlife Epidemiology

Ophidiomyces qPCR - Verified: 05/23/16 9:12 AM by ED3

Test Name	Specimen	Specimen ID	Results
Ophidiomyces qPCR	# 1 Tissue NOS	16T119 jaw	14436.00 <u>POSITIVE</u>
Ophidiomyces qPCR	# 2 Tissue NOS	16T119 skin	1783.00 <u>POSITIVE</u>

**General Test Comment:*

A sample is considered positive if the starting copy number was greater than 10 copies of Ophidiomyces per reaction. It does not indicate active infection, only presence of the DNA. However, a positive result in the presence of clinical signs, a strong association with Snake Fungal Disease should be considered. Due to changes in fungal shedding, differences in sampling techniques, and disease-related changes in depth of the fungus, fungal copies do not always correspond to degree severity. If therapeutic monitoring is needed, then maintaining consistent sampling procedures is warranted. A negative result indicates that the DNA was not present in the sample. This may be due to: 1) the animal is truly negative; 2) sampling or handling technique was inadequate to sample the Ophidiomyces, or; 3) The fungus is within deeper tissue layers and swabbing was not able to reach the fungus.

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